

RHODANINE-N-SALICYLIC ACID AND ITS USE IN THE ESTIMATION OF THORIUM

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Rhodanine-N-salicylic acid has been used for the estimation of thorium. On the basis of the weight of the complex obtained, a probable structure has been proposed for the thorium complex. Additional support in favour of the proposed structure has been provided by ignition of a definite weight of the complex to ThO_2 .

Many organic compounds like fumaric acid, *m*-nitrobenzoic acid, phenylarsonic acid, sodium anthranilate and sebacic acid etc. have been used as precipitating reagents for thorium (Metzger, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 24, 901; Neish, *Chem. News*, 1904, 90, 196; Riss and Foggs, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 893; Goto, *J. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1934, 55, 1156; James and Smith, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 34, 281).

Some of these reagents have also been successfully used for separation of thorium from rare earths. Raghava Rao and his co-workers have used chloro- and amino-benzoic acids, phenoxyacetic acids and trimethylgallic acid etc. for the quantitative estimation and separation of thorium (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 457, 459, 81). Datta and Banerjee have also successfully employed 2:4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid and 5-iodoanthranilic acid for the same purpose (*ibid.*, 1954, 31, 397, 229, 773, 779).

In course of our investigations on thiohydantoins, thiazolidones and rhodanines, we studied the possibility of their use as precipitating agents for thorium. In preliminary screening experiments, all these reagents, except rhodanines, failed to precipitate thorium completely and quantitatively.

EXPERIMENTAL

Rhodanine-N-salicylic Acid.—Dithiocarbamate of *p*-aminosalicylic acid was prepared by taking a mixture of *p*-aminosalicylic acid (13.5 g.) and KOH (11.2 g.) in water (50 c.c.) in a round bottomed flask fitted with a mechanical stirrer and surrounded by an ice-bath. The temperature was not allowed to exceed 10°. CS_2 (7.5 c.c.) was slowly run into the flask from a separating funnel. Stirring was continued until the CS_2 layer disappeared, indicating completion of the reaction.

Potassium monochloroacetate was prepared by mixing a solution of KOH (5.6 g.) in water with a solution of monochloroacetic acid (9.4 g.) in water. Sodium carbonate was added till the solution was neutral to litmus.

To the potassium monochloroacetate solution, thus prepared, the dithiocarbamate was added slowly with stirring and good cooling. The stirring was continued for some time more. Then the mixture was added under stirring to HCl (conc., 15-18 c.c.), previously heated to 90° when a yellow precipitate was obtained. It was stirred for one hour more and then allowed to stand in an ice-bath for another hour. The rhodanine was filtered and washed with water and recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 117°, yield 75%. (Found: N, 5.34. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{O}_2\text{NS}_2$ requires N, 5.20 per cent).

Estimation of Thorium.—A stock solution of thorium nitrate was prepared and the thorium content was determined by a standard method using *m*-nitrobenzoic acid.

Thorium nitrate solution (25 c.c.) from the stock solution was taken in a beaker and was made just neutral to Congo red by adding dilute ammonia. An excess of an 1% solution of the reagent in alcohol was added. The necessary amount of the excess reagent was established by a series of experiments in which the amount of reagent was varied from 1:7 to 10-fold excess. The data indicated that a four-fold or a slightly greater excess was adequate. A precipitate appeared immediately. The complex was then warmed on a water-bath for 15 minutes and kept overnight. The complex was filtered in a G₃ crucible, washed with hot water and dried at 110°-115°. The weights of the complex formed in different sets of experiments from the same volume of thorium nitrate solution were found to be nearly the same (Table I). On the basis of the weights, the following formula for the complex is proposed.

[X = residue of 2-mercaptothiazolidone-N-salicylic acid]

TABLE I

Thorium taken (as nitrate in g.)	0.0632	0.0632	0.1264	0.1264	0.1896	0.1896
Weight of complex (g.)	0.1585	0.1625	0.3215	0.3226	0.4776	0.4826
% Thorium (found)	39.87	38.90	39.31	39.18	39.71	39.30
% Thorium (calc. on the basis of the proposed structure)	39.53					

Thorium has also been estimated from the weight of ThO₂ obtained by ignition of the complex formed with the organic reagent. As will appear from Table II, the results compare well with the data obtained by using standard *m*-nitrobenzoic acid method.

TABLE II

Reagent.	ThO ₂ found in g.				
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	0.0948	0.0956	0.0952	0.1906	0.2842
Rhodanine-N-salicylic acid	0.0952	0.0955	0.0951	0.1895	0.2851

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Received September 21, 1955.